
GENERAL ETHICAL GUIDELINES

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Introduction

1. AgroServ Overview

AgroServ features a large consortium of Research Infrastructures (RIs), most of them being in the ESFRI roadmap, with a vast offer of services at all scales, from the molecule to the organism, to the ecosystem, to society at large. AgroServ will facilitate a systemic and holistic approach to understand the threats and challenges agriculture is facing, towards the implementation of a resilient and sustainable agrifood system.

2. Ethical aspects of Access

AgroServ offers a range of access to Transnational (TA) and Virtual (VA) services to facilitate research activities and achieve the objectives of the project (see above). All project submissions will be required to complete an [ethics self-assessment](#), - and those that concern the use of animals, humans (sociology, economy), and plants will undergo additional rigorous evaluation by internal and external experts to ensure that the ethical rules set by the Commission and the host country are adhered to; the Ethical TA committee will develop protocols for the ethical assessment of the submitted TA proposals. The committee will be composed of representatives on ethical and legal issues from each RI.

Ethical Rules and Guidelines of AgroServ

The recommendations in these guidelines for AgroServ are based on the documents from the European Commission ([EU Taxonomy regulation](#) - Do no harm principles 2019/2088), [The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) from ALLEA (ALL European Academies) and the Society for Ecological Restoration ([Code of conduct](#)).

1. Transnational access (TA)

Each application will submit an [ethics self-assessment \(included in the pre-proposal\)](#) which will be approved by the TA committee and the relevant entity(ies) host institutions according to their existing rules and national laws whenever applicable.

The following subjects concerned by ethical issues have been identified:

1. Use of animals: ethical aspects of the use of animals in experiments and implementation of 3R principles (replace, reduce, refine).
 - The use of animals for experiments will be kept to a minimum. All installations in the AgroServ project, and listed in the catalogue, comply with the relevant national and European policies.
2. Use of plants: ethical aspects of using harmful input, new research techniques, breeding, etc.,
3. Interactions with humans: deontology and ethics in social sciences, and privacy aspects (including at Living Labs),
 - Participants and users involved in Living Labs, surveys, focus groups, workshops, or any activity linked with the AgroServ project will be asked to respond on a voluntary basis and will be able to choose whether they want to provide their personal data to be further processed, or not.
 - TA compliance with the ethical guidelines will be ensured. In particular, persons concerned ("data subjects") will be given an "informed consent form" and detailed "information sheets". The consent form and the information sheet which will be kept on file.
4. ABS compliance (Material Transfer Agreement, etc.).

Projects that include animal, human and plant specimens or operations will adhere to the

- "do no harm" principle as described in the [EU Taxonomy regulation](#)
- [Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilisation \(ABS\) to the Convention on Biological Diversity](#)
- Methods in cattle physiology and behaviour research, chapter on [Ethics in experiments on live cattle](#) and [Guidelines to apply for ethical approval of animal experiments](#) from SmartCow.

The [AgroServ Ethics Self-Assessment](#) is in line with the [EUDirective 98/58](#) on the protection of animals kept for farming purposes, [EU Regulation 1099/2009](#) on the protection of animals at the time of killing, [EU Regulation 889/2008](#) on organic production and labelling of organic products and [EU Directive 2010/63](#) on the use of animals for scientific purposes.

2. Data

In compliance with ethical principles, and relevant legislation, of the [AgroServ Ethical Self-Assessment](#) :

Data generated by the project:

The RIs involved in this project have already implemented FAIR and open-access principles in their data management practices and have their own DMPs (as requested for ESFRI RIs). After a possible embargo period, whose duration shall not exceed 1 year after full completion of the project (enforced by the AgroServ [Data Management Plan](#)), that will be a criterion for the eligibility of proposals and the data will be available publicly. The data generated will be in the responsibility of the data owner though this might be different depending on the data generation and/or RI involved.

Personal data:

A Data Protection Officer (DPO) will be appointed for RI or parent institution of the installation and his/her contact details will be made available to all data subjects involved in the research. *In the case, the DPO has not been appointed, please refer to the DPO from the parent organisation.* [GDPR rights](#) of participants will be strictly respected, for example with respect to Right of access, Right to rectification, Right to erasure, Right to restriction of processing, Right to object, Right to data portability, Right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority etc

3. General research integrity and research practices

As per [The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) from ALLEA.

- We abide by the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. The key principles for good research practices are:
 - Research Environment
 - Training, Supervision and Mentoring
 - Research Procedures
 - Safeguards

- Data Practices and Management
 - Collaborative Working
 - Publication and Dissemination
 - Reviewing, Evaluating and Editing
-
- Users will abide by the research integrity rules of their home institution, and are additionally requested to abide by the rules / code of conduct of the partner institutions that host the services defined in the AgroServ project.

4. Resolving conflicts and Ethics violations

Role of the Independent Ethical Advisory Board

The Independent Ethical Advisory Board (IEAB) will be consulted on ethics related issues. It will provide advice on the interpretation and implementation of the general ethical guidelines. Any violation of the present ethical guidelines will be referred to the IEAB, if a resolution is not found between the parties concerned. In the latter case, the IEAB will be informed about the conflict, the means to reach the positive issue, and the outcome. The IEAB will have the possibility to comment and make any recommendation, including re-opening the case.

General Principles

Users and service providers are encouraged to resolve conflicts among the individuals directly involved in the matter, using these Guidelines. If the issue can't be solved amicably, each submitted project - during the "full" application - will need to complete an [ethics self-assessment](#) and a complaint form (which can be found in Annex 1) that will be submitted to the coordinator.

In the following text, the person or group making the complaint is referred to as the "complainant" and the opposing party or group is referred to as the "respondent".

Any departure from the ethical rules should be referred to the coordinator. The complainant will be asked to present its case and any supporting evidence to the coordinator and the respondent will present its own defence and any associated material. If the case can't be solved amicably, the coordinator shall submit it to the IEAB for advice. The IEAB recommendation will then be discussed by the Executive Committee. The parties concerned will be notified of the decision of the Executive Committee without delay.

Complaints should be logged as soon as possible, and before a delay of one year after the possible violation of the ethics has been made or has become apparent . If identified beyond this date, complaints will be lodged 60 days after identification. The Project Coordinator will keep copies of all communications for a period of 5 years after the end of the project after which they will be destroyed, unless requested by the relevant authorities.

Home institutions (e.g universities, government agencies) often have their own ethical policies and will have priority in resolving ethics complaints that concern their employees or students.

Figure 1: Conflict resolution procedures

Procedures for Evaluating Possible Violation

1. These guidelines shall be made public and published on the web site of the project.
2. The complaint must be sent via a form that can be found in annex 1 of this document.
3. Complaints, and departures from ethics shall be referred as soon as possible to the Coordinator
4. The Coordinator will inform the case without delay and inform both the IEAB and the Executive committee.
5. The Coordinator will discuss the issue raised with both parties to evaluate the importance of the case, and the possibility to solve it amicably, on the basis of the ethical guidelines in this document and the references herein.

If the inquiry or complaint is resolved through discussion with these members, no further action will be undertaken. Both parties will sign a complaint agreement (which can be found in Annex 2).

6. Upon reception of the recommendation of the IEAB, the Executive Committee will take a decision.
7. The coordinator will inform the parties of the decision. If the decision is public, the Coordinator will make it public through the web site of AgroServ and any other appropriate means of diffusion.

Actions

Actions will be specific to each case and will be for a specified time or permanent. Possible actions include:

- No action in case no evidence for departure from ethics is found
- A written warning by the coordinator resulting in the prohibition from partaking in the project after a second violation.
- Respondents may be banned from events organised by the AgroServ consortium.

The Coordinator will refer the case to the appropriate authorities.

Procedure of adoption and revision

These procedures will be effective upon adoption by the Executive Committee, following a positive recommendation from the IEAB. They will be revised as needed during the duration of the project.

Appendix 1: Abbreviation list

ABS - Access and benefit sharing

ALLEA: ALL European Academies (federation of academies of sciences and humanities)

DPO - Data Protection Officer

GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation

IEAB - Independent Ethical Advisory Board

LL - Living labs

TA - Transnational Access

VA Virtual Access

Appendix 2: Definition

Partners - Beneficiaries, affiliated and associated entities of the AgroServ Grant Agreement.

Transnational access – free-of-charge access to European research infrastructures.

Users - benefits from the usage of our services

Virtual access - ensures free of charge access to e-infrastructure

Annex 1: Complaint form

I hereby consent to the processing of the personal data that I have provided and declare my agreement with the data protection plan of the project.

AgroServ Ethics Complaint Form

First name: _____ Surname: _____
On behalf of: _____
Address: _____
Town/City: _____
County/State/Province: _____ Postcode: _____
Country: _____ Telephone: _____
Email: _____

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What is the reason for your complaint? Please give precise details (add supporting documentation when necessary).

Please indicate which guidelines your complaint is related to?

What result do you hope to achieve with your complaint?

Annex 2: Complain Agreement

I hereby consent to the processing of the personal data that I have provided and declare my agreement with the data protection plan of the project.

AgroServ Ethics Complaint Agreement

First name: _____ Surname: _____
On behalf of: _____
Address: _____
Town/City: _____
County/State/Province: _____ Postcode: _____
Country: _____ Telephone: _____
Email: _____

.....
What is the reason for your complaint ? Please give a summary of the issue.

Please indicate what conclusion the parties involved reached.

Project Coordinator Signature

Complainant Signature